

27 The consumption of flavonoid-rich *Citrus* extracts has been associated with multiple
28 beneficial effects including anti-inflammatory properties but the potential effects on the
29 inflammatory responses in the gut have not been thoroughly investigated. We used
30 microarrays to search for molecular changes induced in human colon fibroblasts in
31 response to the exposure to a flavanone-rich bitter orange extract under physiological
32 representative conditions. Dietary non-toxic levels of the pre-digested extract induced
33 moderate but significant changes in the expression of genes associated with tissue repair
34 and inflammation. Among the top regulated genes, plasminogen activator inhibitor 1
35 (PAI-1) was downregulated and the matrix metalloproteinase 12 (MMP-12) was
36 upregulated (mRNA and protein levels). Both proteins are involved in extracellular
37 matrix (ECM) remodeling and fibroblasts migration. The extract also affected the
38 fibroblasts migration and reduced monocytes adhesion, but the response was different in
39 unstimulated cells and in cells pre-treated with TNF- α . Collectively these results were
40 indicative of a moderate activation of the colon fibroblasts inflammation-related
41 function after exposure to the extract. Further investigations are required to identify the
42 *in vivo* role of this *Citrus* derived extract in the maintenance of the normal balance in
43 the intestine and in the pathogenesis of inflammatory diseases.

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46 **KEYWORDS:** *in vitro* digestion; intestinal stability; microarrays; MMP-12;
47 migration; monocytes adhesion

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52 INTRODUCTION

53 Inflammation is a normal protective attempt by the organism to eliminate
54 harmful stimuli, such as pathogens or toxins, as well as to initiate the healing and repair
55 process of the damaged tissue. Inflammation is a very complex response that involves
56 different types of cells (neutrophils, mononuclear cells, fibroblasts) as well as a cascade
57 of molecular mediators which are all closely regulated by the organism. Uncontrolled
58 inflammation can lead to chronic diseases such as allergy, rheumatoid arthritis and
59 bowel inflammatory diseases (1). In these cases, anti-inflammatory compounds are
60 therapeutically administered to control the inflammation response. Plants rich in certain
61 flavonoids have been traditionally used for their anti-inflammatory properties, and
62 recently, attention has been given to flavonoids isolated from *Citrus* (2). Flavanones are
63 the flavonoids predominant in *Citrus*, where they are usually found as glycosides
64 (naringin, neohesperidin, hesperidin, etc) (3). These compounds are of commercial
65 interest because of their multitude of applications in the food and pharmaceutical
66 industries. Significantly, much of the bioactivity of *Citrus* flavonoids appears to impact
67 blood and microvascular endothelial cells and thus, inflammation has been an important
68 area of research among the biological actions of *Citrus* flavanones. Hesperidin has been
69 commercialized as a product that improves the permeability and integrity of the
70 capillary lining (4). It has also been reported to exert noticeable *in vivo* anti-
71 inflammatory systemic effects in mice models of lipopolysaccharide (LPS)–induced
72 lung inflammation (5) and of endotoxin-induced infection (6), in rat models of
73 rheumatoid arthritis (7, 8) and against inflammation in mouse skin (9). Naringin also
74 reduces LPS– or infection–induced endotoxin shock in mice (10, 11) and, its aglycone,
75 naringenin, exerts anti-inflammatory properties in macrophages and in human blood
76 (12).

77 There are only a few reports looking at the anti-inflammatory effects of *Citrus*
78 flavonoids in the intestine. Hesperidin has been shown to ameliorate colonic
79 inflammation by reducing colonic damage and colonic mieloperoxidase activity in
80 animal models of trinitrobenzenesulfonic acid (TNBS)- (13) and of dextran sulphate
81 sodium (DSS)-induced experimental colitis (14). Bowel inflammatory diseases are
82 characterized by chronic mucosal inflammation resulting from the transmural
83 infiltration of immune cells (neutrophils, lymphocytes, monocytes) accompanied by the
84 overproduction of oxygen free radicals, ultimately leading to the disruption of the
85 epithelial barrier (1). Colonic subepithelial fibroblasts are critically involved in wound
86 healing and mucosal repair processes due to their ability to synthesize and secrete
87 collagens and various other ECM components which are important molecules for ECM
88 remodeling. It is becoming clear that colon fibroblasts also play an active role in the
89 inflammation response in the gut since they affect the recruitment and activation of the
90 immune cells through their synthesis of cytokines, chemokines, eicosanoids, adhesion
91 proteins and other inflammatory mediators (15).

92 To date, the potential effects of plant derived flavanone-rich extracts in the
93 inflammatory responses in the gut have not been investigated in great detail. In the
94 present work, genome-wide microarrays analyses followed by differential expression
95 and functional analysis were used to investigate the response of human colon fibroblasts
96 (CCD-18Co) to treatment with a bitter orange extract enriched in several flavanones
97 under conditions representative of those that may occur *in vivo*. This study also sought
98 to examine the phenotypic response of the cells by looking at indications of improved
99 migration and monocytes adhesion to colon fibroblasts after the treatment.

100

101 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

102 **Materials.** The soluble extract from bitter orange kindly provided by Zoster S.A.
103 (Murcia, Spain) was composed of: flavonoids (45–55%), water (3–5%), proteins (11–13%),
104 pectins (12–14%), cellulosic material (0–1%), ashes (2–3%), vitamins (1000–1200 ppm vitamin
105 C and traces of vitamins B1, B2 and B6), β -carotene (3–5 ppm) and other components (3–5%).
106 On arrival, the extract (a hygroscopic brown powder, 2.1% humidity), was kept in a tightly
107 closed container within a dessicator at room temperature. Fresh solutions of the extract were
108 prepared by dissolving 0.1g of the powder extract in 50 mL of water (0.2%). Pepsin from
109 porcine stomach mucosa (pepsin A, EC 3.4.23.1), pancreatin from porcine pancreas (4 g/L, 1.6
110 $\times 10^{-3}$ U.S. Pharmacopeia (USP) specifications) and bile extract mixture (25 g/L, containing a
111 mixture of sodium cholate and sodium deoxycholate) were all from Sigma (Steinheim,
112 Germany). Naringin (naringenin–7–O–neohesperidoside), hesperidin (hesperetin–7–O–
113 rutinoside), neohesperidin (hesperetin–7–O–neohesperidoside), naringenin (4',5,7–
114 trihydroxyflavanone), hesperetin (3',5,7–trihydroxy–4'–methoxy flavanone) and isosakuranetin
115 (5,7–dihydroxy–4'–methoxyflavanone) were purchased from Extrasynthese (Genay, France).
116 Human recombinant TNF- α was from Sigma (Steinheim, Germany). All other chemicals were
117 of analytical / HPLC grade. Ultrapure Millipore water was used for all solutions.

118 **In Vitro Digestion.** The extract solution was subjected to successive *in vitro* salival,
119 gastric and pancreatic digestion. Gastric and pancreatic incubations were carried out following a
120 previously published method (16) with some modifications. Briefly, 50 mL of extract solution
121 were first incubated with 200 μ L of fresh human saliva on a magnetic stirrer for 5 minutes.
122 Based on *in vivo* results (17), the orange extract solution was then gradually adjusted to pH 2.0
123 by sequential addition of 0.1N HCl and pepsin in a shaking bath as follows: time 0, initial pH
124 7.6, addition of 25% of pepsin; time 15 min, pH 5.5, addition of 25% of pepsin; time 30 min,
125 pH 3.0, addition of the remaining 50% of pepsin; time 60 min, final pH 1.9 (total pepsin added:
126 15750 IU). A 20 mL sample of the pepsin digest was then neutralized with NaHCO₃ before
127 addition of 5 mL of pancreatin–bile extract mixture and further incubation of the mixture (pH
128 7.5) for an additional 2.0 h. Control samples were run in parallel and consisted of an equivalent
129 volume of ultrapure water subjected to the same digestion process (i.e. contains the mixture of

130 enzymes + salts). At the end of each digestion stage, 1 mL samples were taken and filtered (0.2
131 μm) prior to analysis of the flavanones using high performance liquid chromatography-diode
132 array detection (HPLC-DAD).

133 ***In Vivo* Gastrointestinal Stability of the Flavanones.** Male Sprague-Dawley rats
134 ($n=15$; Harlan Interfauna Ibérica, S.L., Barcelona, Spain) weighing 232 ± 14 g were kept in the
135 Experimental Animal Facility of the University of Murcia (Spain). The study followed a
136 protocol approved by the local animal Ethics Committee and the Local Government and was in
137 accordance with the recommendations of the European Union regarding animal experimentation
138 (Directive of the European Council 86/609/EC). Rats were housed in a room with controlled
139 temperature (22 ± 2 °C), $55 \pm 10\%$ relative humidity and a 12 h light-dark cycle and had free
140 access to tap water and a rat standard chow (Panlab, Barcelona, Spain). The animals were
141 slightly anaesthetized by intramuscular administration of a mixture (1:1 v/v; 0.32 mL/kg body
142 weight) of xylazine (Calier Laboratories, Barcelona, Spain) and ketamine (Merial Laboratories,
143 Barcelona, Spain) and 150 mg of the orange extract (63.15 mg of total flavanones) dissolved in
144 0.5 mL of water were administered via gastric gavage. At 1, 2, 6, 8, 12 and 24 h after
145 administration, the animals were anaesthetized (xylazine:ketamine 1:1 v/v; 1.0 mL/kg body
146 weight), sacrificed by heart puncture exsanguination and the stomach, small and large intestine
147 removed. The content of these organs were washed out with cold phosphate buffered saline
148 (PBS), weighed into 15 mL sterile tubes, frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 °C until
149 extraction and analysis of the flavanones. Extractions were carried out following a reported
150 protocol (18).

151 **Analysis of Flavanones by HPLC-DAD.** Samples (original extract, digested aliquots,
152 culture medium or rat lumen content) were all filtered (0.2 μm) and analyzed by HPLC-DAD to
153 determine the composition and recovery of soluble flavanones. Separations were achieved on a
154 250 x 4 mm i.d., 5 μm , C_{18} Mediterranean Sea column (Teknokroma, Barcelona, Spain) using
155 water:formic acid (99:1, v/v) (A) and acetonitrile (B) as the mobile phases at a flow rate of 1
156 mL/min. The linear gradient started with 7% solvent B in solvent A reaching 30% solvent B at
157 25 min which was kept up to minute 30. At 36 min the gradient reached 60% of solvent B and

158 90% at 37 min up to 42 min then back to the initial conditions again and kept in isocratic
159 conditions up to 50 min. Flavanones were identified by their spectroscopic properties.
160 Chromatograms were recorded at 280 nm and quantification was done by comparison with
161 authentic synthetic external standards dissolved in DMSO. Analyses were replicated (at least
162 n=3) and results are given as mean values \pm SD.

163 **Cell Culture and Cell Treatment.** The myofibroblast-like cell line CCD-18Co,
164 derived from a colonic mucosal biopsy, was obtained from the American Type Culture
165 Collection (ATCC) (Rockville, MD, USA). Cells were grown in Eagle's minimum essential
166 medium (EMEM) supplemented with 2 mM L-glutamine, 0.1 mM nonessential amino acids, 1
167 mM sodium pyruvate, 1.5 g/L sodium bicarbonate, 100 U/mL penicillin, 100 μ g/mL
168 streptomycin (Gibco, Invitrogen S.A., Barcelona, Spain) and 10% v/v fetal bovine serum (FBS)
169 at a final pH 7.2–7.4 and maintained at 37°C under a 5% CO₂/ 95% air atmosphere at constant
170 humidity. Cells were seeded at 6000 cells/cm² on 6-well plates (RNA extraction) or 10 cm
171 plates (protein extracts) (Nunc, Roskilde, Denmark), allowed to adhere for 48 h and treated on
172 day 5–6 after seeding (~80% confluence) as follows: i) digested orange extract (~60 μ M total
173 flavanones in the culture medium); ii) non digested orange extract (~60 μ M total flavanones in
174 the culture medium); iii) mixture of 6 major flavanones (~60 μ M total flavanones in the culture
175 medium). Cells were exposed to each of the extracts or compounds for 12 h, 24 h and/or 48 h.
176 The orange extract was dissolved in water whereas the flavanones were dissolved in DMSO
177 (<0.1% in the culture medium) and filtered (0.2 μ m) prior to addition to the culture media.
178 Control cells were treated with control digesta (mix of enzymes and salts + water) or DMSO
179 (<0.1%). In a second set of experiments, the colon cells were deprived from serum for 24 h
180 (0.1% FBS). Next, the cells were subjected to an inflammatory stimulus using TNF- α (20
181 ng/mL) for 8 h prior to treatment with the non digested orange extract (~60 μ M total flavanones
182 in the culture medium) for a further 24 h. All treatments were carried out in triplicate and with
183 cells between passages 30 and 35. To discard cells cytotoxicity caused by a pronounced shift of
184 the osmolality and/or the pH of the culture medium when incubated with excessive quantities of
185 digested extract, we measured the pH (Neutralit, pH 5.5–9.0, Merck) and the osmolality vapour

186 pressure osmometer 5520 (VAPRO, Wescor) in the culture medium as well as cell proliferation
187 and cell viability after 12 h and 24 h of exposure to increasing amounts of the digested orange
188 extract (2–470 μ M total equivalent flavanones concentration in the culture media). The stability
189 of the flavanones in the culture medium was determined by monitoring the concentration of
190 each of the flavanones by HPLC-DAD at different time points during the incubation.

191 Human acute monocytic THP-1 cells were obtained from the European Collection of
192 Cells Cultured (ECACC) (Salisbury, UK). Cells were maintained in RPMI 1640 culture media
193 containing 10% FBS, 2 mM L-glutamine, 100 U/mL penicillin and 100 μ g/mL streptomycin
194 (Gibco, Invitrogen S.A., Barcelona, Spain) at a final pH 7.2–7.4 and maintained at 37°C under a
195 5% CO₂/95% air atmosphere at constant humidity. Cells were seeded at 3–5 \times 10⁵ cells/mL on
196 either 25 or 75 cm² flasks (Nunc, Roskilde, Denmark). Cells were subcultivated every two days
197 (cells concentration in the culture media always below 8 \times 10⁵ cells/mL). All experiments were
198 carried out in triplicate and with cells between passages 10 and 15.

199 **Cell Proliferation and Viability.** At the end of each treatment, trypsinized cells (2.5
200 g/L trypsin, 0.2 g/L EDTA) were suspended in culture medium, counted using a
201 haemocytometer and viability measured using Trypan blue dye exclusion. Results of
202 proliferation and viability in treated cells are presented in comparison to untreated cells. Data
203 are presented as mean values \pm SD from three independent experiments (n=3 plates per
204 experiment).

205 **RNA Extraction.** Total RNA was isolated using an RNeasy mini kit (Quiagen,
206 Barcelona, Spain). Concentration and purity were checked using the Nanodrop
207 spectrophotometer system. Only samples with a ratio Abs₂₆₀/Abs₂₈₀ between 1.8 and 2.1 were
208 used for microarrays experiments. The integrity of the ribosomal RNA was further checked
209 using agarose gel electrophoresis (1%). Treatments and extractions were done in triplicate.

210 **Microarray Analysis.** A search for potential candidate genes for which transcription
211 levels may have been modulated in the colon cells following exposure to the flavanones extract
212 was performed using Affymetrix microarray analysis (GeneChip Affymetrix microarray HG

213 U133 Plus 2.0) following the manufacturer's one-cycle protocol. Microarray data were Robust-
214 Multi-Array (RMA)-normalized and tested for differential gene expression using a *t-test* and
215 FDR adjustment for multiple testing implemented with software Gene Expression Pattern
216 Analysis Suite (GEPAS) (19). Probes were considered to exhibit significant expression changes
217 when they met the two following criteria: 1) FDR <0.2 ($p < 0.005$); 2) changes were ≥ 1.25 or
218 ≤ 0.80 (ratio treated/control). To identify significantly altered biological pathways and top
219 regulated functions associated to responsive genes, Ingenuity Pathways Analysis (IPA) (20) was
220 used. Minimum Information About a Microarray Experiment (MIAME) compliant data from
221 control and treated CCD-18Co cells after exposure to the flavanones enriched orange extract
222 have been deposited in NCBI's Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) (21) and are accessible
223 through GEO Series accession number GSE15322.

224 **RT-PCR.** Changes in the expression of five selected genes responding to the treatment
225 with the flavanones extract were further assessed by one-step quantitative RT-PCR (Taqman
226 system, Applied Biosystems, ABI, Madrid, Spain). Primers and probes for the genes were
227 selected from Assays-on-demand (ABI, Madrid, Spain) and are as follows: *SERPINE1* (Serpine
228 peptidase inhibitor, clade E (nexin, plasminogen activator inhibitor type 1) member 1),
229 (Hs00167155_m1); *MMP12* (Matrix metalloproteinase 12 (macrophage elastase)),
230 (Hs00899662_m1); *SMAD3* (SMAD family member 3), (Hs00232219_m1); *TGFBR2*
231 (Transforming growth factor, beta receptor II (70/80kDa)), (Hs00234253_m1); *SMURF2*
232 (SMAD specific E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 2), (Hs00224203_m1) (_m indicates an assay
233 whose probe spans an exon junction and will not detect genomic DNA). The one-step real-time
234 RT-PCRs were run on the ABI 7500 system following manufacturer's conditions, using a total
235 reaction volume of 25 μ L in a MicroAmp Optical 96-well plate covered by optical adhesive
236 covers and using Taqman Universal Master Mix (ABI, Madrid, Spain). All assays for a
237 particular gene were undertaken at the same time under identical conditions and in triplicate.
238 The expression levels of target genes were normalized to the levels of glyceraldehyde-3-
239 phosphate dehydrogenase (*GAPDH*; Hs99999905_m1) utilizing a standard curve method for
240 quantification.

241 **Western Blot Analysis.** Following treatment, cells were washed twice with PBS and
242 lysed with 0.5 or 1 mL of ice-cold lysis RIPA buffer containing a mixture of protease inhibitors
243 (Roche). Lysates were centrifuged at 15000×g for 15 min at 4 °C, and protein concentration was
244 determined by the Bradford's method. Equal amounts of protein (10 µg per lane) were separated
245 on a 10% SDS polyacrylamide gel (SDS-PAGE) and transferred to polyvinylidene difluoride
246 membranes (Amersham Biosciences, Buckinghamshire, UK) by electroblotting. The
247 membranes were washed and incubated for 2 h with the primary antibodies: serpine1 (~40KDa),
248 (Affinity Bioreagents, ABR, Madrid, Spain) at 1:1000; polyclonal antibody anti-MMP-12
249 (MBL international corporation, Woburn, MA) at 1:250; SMAD3 (48-52KDa) (ABR) at 1:500;
250 TGFBR2 (~70KDa) (Abcam, Cambridge, UK) at 1:500; SMURF2 (~86KDa) (Abcam) at
251 1:1000 followed by 1 h with anti-mouse IgG (Sigma-Aldrich Química S.A., Madrid, Spain) or
252 anti-rabbit IgG (Sigma-Aldrich) horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-linked secondary antibody at
253 1:5000. Membranes were developed with ECL Plus (Amersham Biosciences, Buckinghamshire,
254 UK) according to the manufacturer's instructions and exposed to X-ray film. GAPDH antibody
255 (~36KDa) (ABR) at 1:2500 was used to control for protein loading. Western blot analyses were
256 done at least in triplicate.

257 **Cell Migration: Cell Culture Wound Healing Assay.** Confluent monolayers of CCD-
258 18Co cells were scraped away horizontally with a sterile pipette tip. Media, dislodged cells and
259 debris were aspirated, washed once with PBS and cells were incubated with fresh medium
260 (0.1% FBS) for 24 h. Next, the cells were treated with TNF-α (20 ng/mL) for 8 h prior to
261 treatment with the non digested orange extract (~60 µM total flavanones in the culture medium)
262 for a further 24 h. Randomly selected views along the scraped line were photographed on each
263 well at the end of treatment, using a phase contrast inverted microscope and a CCD camera
264 attached to the microscope. The change in the area of the experimental condition was compared
265 with that of the corresponding control. Results are representative of two to four experiments.

266 **Monocyte-Fibroblast Cell Adhesion Assay.** Monocyte-colon fibroblast cell adhesion
267 was evaluated using the human leukemia monocytic THP-1 cells. Monocytes (1×10⁶ cells/mL)
268 were resuspended in PBS, labeled with 5 µM calcein (Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) for

269 30 min at 37 °C and wash twice with PBS before addition to the fibroblasts. Colon fibroblasts
270 cultured in 96-wells plates to confluence were incubated with fresh medium (10% or 0.1% FBS)
271 for 24 h. Next, cells were inflamed using TNF- α (20 ng/mL) for 8 h prior to treatment with the
272 non digested orange extract (~60 μ M total flavanones in the culture medium) for a further 24 h.
273 After treatment, the colon fibroblasts were co-incubated with calcein-prelabeled monocytes
274 (2×10^5 cells per well) for 1 h at 37 °C. Non-adhering cells were removed, and the cells washed
275 twice with PBS before fluorescence was measured with a fluorescence-detecting microplate
276 reader (Fluostar Galaxy, BMG Lab. Technologies v5.0) using excitation at 492 nm and
277 emission at 520 nm.

278 **Statistical analysis.** Results are presented as mean values \pm SD (at least n=3). Where
279 indicated, differences between groups (control vs. treated) were compared using an unpaired *t*-
280 Student's test (except for microarray analysis, see specific section). Results with a two-sided *p*
281 value <0.05 or <0.01 were considered statistically significant.

282

283 RESULTS

284 **Stability of Flavanones Present in the Orange Extract During Gastro-**
285 **Intestinal Digestion.** HPLC-DAD analysis of the orange extract (0.2% in water)
286 showed that the extract comprised of approximately 42.1% soluble flavanones with two
287 most abundant compounds, naringin ($24.5 \pm 2.6\%$) and neohesperidin ($11.4 \pm 0.8\%$),
288 followed by hesperidin ($1.7 \pm 0.4\%$), naringenin ($0.4 \pm 0.1\%$), hesperetin ($0.4 \pm 0.1\%$)
289 and isosakuranetin ($0.2 \pm 0.1\%$) (% of the powder extract; mean \pm SD; n=7). The
290 structures of the main flavanones constituents of the bitter orange extract are included in
291 **Figure 1.** Other minor components with spectral properties similar to those of
292 flavanones amounted for $3.5 \pm 0.8\%$ of the total compounds. The levels of soluble
293 flavanones were not altered after the salival, gastric or pancreatic phases of the *in vitro*
294 digestion. These results show that the major flavanones present in the bitter orange

295 extract are stable under the *in vitro* conditions assayed and suggest that *in vivo*, these
296 compounds may remain constant throughout the small intestine and reach the large
297 intestine in their original molecular form.

298 To validate the *in vitro* stability of the flavanones and to confirm the presence of
299 these intact molecules in the gastrointestinal tract, the luminal contents of the stomach,
300 small and large intestine from rats dosed with the flavanones extract were analyzed by
301 HPLC-DAD. The results are presented in **Table 1**. Around 33% and 18% of the
302 administered flavanones were recovered, from the stomach and from the small intestine
303 respectively, one hour after dosing and were still detected in both sections of the gut
304 even after 12 h of the dose administration. The flavanones were first detected in the
305 colon 2 h after the dosing and the levels of these compounds were found highest at 6
306 and 12 h after the dosing. At 24 h, some flavanones were still detected in the lumen of
307 the stomach and of the small and large intestines (approximately 345 μM flavanones for
308 an estimated 2 mL rat colon volume). The maximum percentage of total flavanones
309 recovered was approximately 72% of the administered dose.

310 **Expression Changes Induced in Human Colon Fibroblasts by the Digested**
311 **Flavanone-rich Orange Extract.** Quantities of filtered (0.2 μm) digested orange
312 extract equivalent to 2.0 to 60 μM of total flavanones added to the culture media or the
313 corresponding control digestion mix did not alter appreciably the pH values (7.0–7.5) of
314 the culture medium and the osmolality was within the range tolerated by human cells
315 (260–320 mOsm/L). Within this range of concentrations, the treated colon cells (12 h or
316 24 h) exhibited similar viability (>90%) and proliferation values (>95%) as the control
317 cells (treated with the mixture of salts + enzymes) or the untreated cells (EMEM). Also,
318 the major flavanones present in the extract were stable in the culture conditions even
319 after 24 of incubation (results not shown).

320 Microarray analysis were used to investigate gene expression changes induced in
321 colon fibroblasts by the pre-digested orange extract at a dose that did not cause
322 cytotoxicity or inhibition of cell proliferation (i.e. we were not investigating anti-
323 proliferative effects) and that was representative of the quantities that may be found in
324 the colon lumen from the diet. We therefore chose to treat the colon cells with the
325 highest quantity of digested orange extract that did not inhibit cell proliferation (~60 μ M
326 total flavanones in the culture media) and for the largest period of time at which the
327 flavanones were proved to be stable in the culture media, i.e. 24h. After exposure, a
328 total of 705 probes were shown to exhibit moderate but significant expression changes
329 in treated cells against cells treated with the control digesta. The significantly regulated
330 probes and their ratios were uploaded into the IPA software in order to identify genes
331 that could be potentially involved in specific diseases, molecular cell functions and
332 physiological processes and to pinpoint canonical pathways in which those genes are
333 involved and may have been affected in the colon cells by the treatment. Modulated
334 genes were primarily associated with inflammatory diseases, immune response and
335 processes of tissue repair and fibrosis. The principal molecular and cell functions that
336 may have been affected in the treated cells were cell migration and adhesion and
337 recruitment of immune cells. A selection of genes exhibiting significant expression
338 changes in the colon fibroblasts after exposure to the digested orange extract and that
339 are associated to the role of intestinal subepithelial fibroblasts on inflammation and
340 repair processes in the gut is presented in **Table 2**. A number of interleukins,
341 chemokines and prostaglandin synthases were all found to be upregulated whereas
342 several extracellular components, collagens and growth factor related genes were both
343 down- and upregulated in the treated cells. Among the top regulated molecules we

344 detected a significant downregulation of the serine protease inhibitor *Serpine1* or *PAI-1*
345 as well as an upregulation of *MMP-12* (macrophage elastase).

346 We selected *PAI-1* and *MMP-12* as well as several related signaling molecules,
347 *TGFβR2*, *SMAD3* and *SMURF2* to further confirm expression changes in response to
348 the digested orange extract exposure. For each gene, RT-PCR reactions were performed
349 in aliquots of the same mRNA used for microarrays (cells treated for 24 h) and in
350 mRNA prepared from independent experiments (cells treated for 12 h and 24 h; each
351 experiment consisted of triplicate mRNA samples extracted from three separate wells).
352 RT-PCR results are presented as relative expression changes (T/C) in **Figure 2A** and
353 were in good agreement with the Affymetrix microarrays results. We also compared the
354 protein levels between the lysates from control and treated cells using Western blots
355 (**Figure 2B**). We found that the protein levels of PAI-1 and SMURF2 were consistently,
356 although not significantly, downregulated (0.6 ± 0.2 (n=5) and 0.7 ± 0.1 (n=3),
357 respectively) and the levels of MMP-12 were augmented (1.3 ± 0.1 , n=7) after 24 h
358 exposure to the digested orange extract. Since no differences in the protein levels of
359 TGFβR2 or SMAD3 were detected between the control and treated cells, we did not
360 continue the analysis of these two genes.

361 **Expression Changes Caused by the Whole Orange Extract and Not By**
362 **Main Flavanones Constituents.** We next wanted to discard that the observed effects
363 might have been caused by artifacts or other molecules formed during the *in vitro*
364 digestion process. For this purpose we examined whether the observed changes in the
365 three selected markers (*PAI-1*, *MMP-12* and *SMURF2*) were still induced in the colon
366 cells exposed to undigested orange extract at the equivalent concentration of total
367 flavanones (60 μM) (**Figure 3A and 3B**). We found that *PAI-1* gene expression was
368 downregulated by 0.4 ± 0.1 , 0.3 ± 0.1 and 0.6 ± 0.1 after 12 h, 24 h and 48 h of

369 exposure to the undigested orange extract (n=3; $p<0.01$ for 24h). This was further
370 confirmed at the protein level by a small decrease of PAI-1 at the three time points
371 tested significant after 48 h of treatment (0.5 ± 0.1 , n=3, $p<0.05$). MMP-12 was also up-
372 regulated in the colon fibroblasts after exposure to the undigested extract at the mRNA
373 level (3.7 ± 0.3 , 3.3 ± 0.2 , 3.9 ± 0.7) and at the protein level (1.3 ± 0.2 , 1.4 ± 0.2 , $1.2 \pm$
374 0.3) after 12 h, 24 h and 48 h of treatment, respectively. *SMURF2* was downregulated at
375 the mRNA levels but no changes in the protein levels were detected.

376 We next determined whether the observed changes in the levels of PAI-1, MMP-
377 12 and SMURF2 were specifically caused by the main flavanones present in the extract.
378 Exposure of the colon fibroblasts to a mixture of the six major flavanones present in the
379 orange extract at a equivalent individual and total concentration in the culture medium
380 ($60 \mu\text{M}$) induced the transcription levels of *MMP-12* by 2-3 times above the control
381 cells but failed to produce any of the other observed changes indicating that the main
382 flavanones were not responsible for all the changes and that other components in the
383 extract may be responsible for or contribute to them.

384 **Similar Changes Induced by Orange Extract in PAI-1, MMP-12 and**
385 **SMURF2 in TNF- α Stimulated Colon Fibroblasts.** In a second set of experiments,
386 TNF- α -treated colon fibroblasts (20 ng/mL , 8 h) were then exposed to the orange
387 extract for 24 h and the expression levels of *PAI-1*, *MMP-12* and *SMURF2* were
388 measured (**Figure 4**). TNF- α induced the expression levels of *PAI-1* (T/C, 9.3 ± 0.8 ,
389 n=3; $p<0.01$) which were subsequently downregulated to approximately half the value
390 (5.1 ± 0.7 ; $p<0.01$) after the treatment with the orange extract. Treatment of the colon
391 cells with TNF- α and the orange extract further upregulated the mRNA levels of *MMP-*
392 *12* (23.4 ± 2.2 ; $p<0.01$) whereas the cytokine had no effect on *SMURF2* expression (1.1

393 ± 0.1) which was still slightly downregulated (0.7 ± 0.1) in the inflamed fibroblasts by
394 the orange extract.

395 **Phenotypic Changes Induced in the Colon Fibroblasts by the Orange**
396 **Extract.** To determine whether the observed gene expression changes were associated
397 with an effect in some of the modulated cell and molecular functions detected by the
398 IPA analysis (i.e. cell migration and recruitment of immune cells), the phenotypic
399 response of the colon fibroblasts to the treatment with the orange extract was further
400 evaluated. Fibroblasts migration is an important factor in wound repair and we therefore
401 investigated whether the orange extract affected the CCD-18Co cells migration using
402 the cell culture wound healing assay. The data show that, exposure of the colon
403 fibroblasts to TNF- α (**Figure 5D**), to the orange extract (**Figure 5E**) or to the cytokine
404 followed by the orange extract (**Figure 5F**) inhibited cell migration in comparison to
405 control untreated cells (**Figure 5C**). However, treatment with the TNF- α followed by
406 exposure to the orange extract (**Figure 5F**) increased slightly cell migration when
407 compared to the treatment with the cytokine or the extract alone (**Figures 5D** and **5E**,
408 respectively). In addition, and as a measurement of chemotaxis of immune cells, we
409 determined effects of exposure to the orange extract on the capacity of the fibroblasts to
410 adhere monocytes. Exposure of the cultured colon fibroblasts to the orange extract alone
411 enhanced the adhesion of monocytes most significantly ($p < 0.01$) when the fibroblasts
412 were cultured in 10% serum containing medium (**Figure 6**). TNF- α treatment greatly
413 enhanced THP-1 cell adhesion but exposure of the inflamed cells to the orange extract
414 did not have any further effect on the monocytes adhesion.

415

416 **DISCUSSION**

417 The approach to use orally ingested flavonoids or flavonoid-rich extracts with
418 preventive or therapeutic uses is controversial. Low bioavailability and loss of function
419 during digestion and metabolism are two critical arguments against the efficacy of
420 dietary supplementation with these compounds. Like for other flavonoids, the efficiency
421 of absorption of flavanones has been shown to be poor and relatively high quantities of
422 the orally ingested flavanones can pass through the small intestine and reach the colon
423 in their original molecular form (22). In the colon, the glycosides (e.g. naringin,
424 hesperidin, neohesperidin) may be deglycosylated to aglycones (e.g. naringenin,
425 hesperetin) and further transformed into more simple phenolic compounds. Despite
426 microbial metabolism, a proportion of the glycosides and aglycones may remain intact
427 in the lumen for several hours (23, 24). In this study, we were able to detect and
428 quantify the major flavanones present in an orange extract both in the small intestine
429 and in the colon of rats, even 12 and 24 hours after the oral administration of the extract.
430 These results corroborate that dietary flavanones can remain unaltered for several hours
431 in the colon where, they may be absorbed and/or interact with the mucosa and exert
432 some of their biological effects by modifying gene and protein expression. We therefore
433 investigated the effects of a flavanone-rich bitter orange extract on the transcriptomic
434 profile of a human colon cell model (CCD-18Co) under conditions that were
435 representative of the physiological situation. Colon fibroblasts were exposed for 12 and
436 24 h to the orange extract subjected to *in vitro* gastro-duodenal digestion at a final dose
437 that did not exert any toxic effects on the cells (60 μ M total flavanones). We considered
438 this dose to be representative of the levels of flavanones that may be achieved in the
439 colon lumen after oral intake since estimated colon concentrations of total dietary
440 polyphenols may range from 100 μ M to 3 mM (25, 26). Also, we measured a
441 concentration of \sim 345 μ M total flavanones in the colon of rats after an oral dose of

442 63.15 mg of flavanones (human equivalent dose (HED): ~3g for a 70 Kg person). Based
443 on all the above a concentration of approximately 60 μ M of total flavanones in the
444 colon is not unreasonable.

445 We examined the response of colon fibroblasts, because they are a non-
446 cancerous cell line and because these cells constitute an important and active component
447 in the maintenance of the intestinal mucosa. Although colon fibroblasts lie underneath
448 the gut epithelium and are less likely to be in direct contact with the luminal digesta,
449 transient increases in the permeability of tight junction make possible the passage of
450 many nutrients and small molecules (4000-5500 Da) through the paracellular route
451 allowing for direct contact of luminal content with the cells underneath the epithelium
452 (27). Intestine fibroblasts are actively involved in wound healing and intestinal
453 epithelium restitution through the controlled remodeling of ECM and the migration of
454 activated fibroblasts to the site of the wound. Activated fibroblasts show upregulated
455 expression and enhanced secretion of ECM components such as collagen IV, laminin as
456 well as matrix metalloproteases, MMPs. In addition, intestinal fibroblasts are thought to
457 mediate information between the intestinal epithelium and the immune system playing
458 an active role both in the gut physiologic immune response and during pathological
459 inflammation. Activated fibroblasts also produce multiple mediators of inflammation
460 such as growth factors, adhesion molecules, chemokines, cytokines and prostaglandins.
461 These molecules are critical players in directing the balance between physiological and
462 pathophysiological inflammation and in coordinating multiple cell types during the
463 wound healing and epithelial barrier repair and maintenance (15, 28). Under the
464 experimental conditions chosen for our study, treated colon fibroblasts exhibited
465 moderate changes in the expression of groups of genes associated with tissue repair and
466 inflammation. The cells responded to treatment by modulating the levels of expression

467 of multiple ECM components, e.g. upregulation of collagens type IV, laminin and
468 metalloproteinase MMP-12 and both up- and downregulation of several protease
469 inhibitors (serpins). The cells response also involved transcriptional changes for several
470 chemokines, interleukins, growth factors and prostaglandin synthases.

471 Among the top regulated genes in the treated colon CCD-18Co fibroblasts, we
472 found downregulation of the expression of PAI-1 and upregulation of MMP-12 (both at
473 the mRNA and protein levels). PAI-1, a member of the serine protease inhibitors, is a
474 negative regulator of plasminogen conversion to plasmin (a fibrinolytic protein) (29)
475 whereas the metalloproteinase MMP-12 (a macrophage elastase) is able to degrade a
476 range of ECM components (elastin, type IV collagen, laminin, etc) (30). Reduced levels
477 of PAI-1 and increased levels of MMP-12 may contribute to focalized ECM
478 degradation, favoring cell detachment and cell migration (31, 32). Both PAI-1 and
479 MMP-12 have been associated to inflammatory reactions in the intestine mucosa (33,
480 34) and pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α are strong stimulators of PAI-1 (35)
481 and of MMP-12 (36) while it reduces fibroblasts migration (37). In our study, TNF- α
482 induced greatly the expression levels of PAI-1 and MMP-12 in the CCD-18Co colon
483 fibroblasts and this was accompanied by a reduction in cell migration in comparison to
484 untreated control cells. On the other hand, the cytokine-orange extract-treated cells
485 showed a significant decrease in PAI-1 expression and a further induction of MMP-12
486 concomitant with a noticeable increase in cell migration in comparison to the cells
487 treated with the cytokine alone. These results indicated that, in the presence of TNF- α ,
488 changes in the ability of colon fibroblasts to migrate may be associated with changes in
489 the levels of PAI-1 whereas MMP-12 does not seem to have an effect. Reports on the
490 effects of MMP-12 in migration are scarce. Whereas increased digestion of ECM matrix
491 by addition of soluble elastase contributes to lung fibroblast migration (38), MMP-12

492 does not have seem to have any effects on smooth muscle cells (SMC) migration (39)
493 suggesting that the effects may be cell dependent. Conversely, when the colon
494 fibroblasts were treated with the orange extract in the absence of TNF- α , although the
495 expression levels of PAI-1 were diminished compared to the control cells, cell
496 migration was also impaired. These results are in agreement with reported properties of
497 PAI-1 for which both over- and underexpression have been associated to migration
498 inhibition (40). The response may be associated to cell status (unstimulated vs inflamed
499 cells). It has also been suggested that precise physiologic concentrations of PAI-1 are
500 required for optimum migration (40). Additionally, the orange extract induced the
501 adhesion of monocytes to the colon fibroblasts in the absence of the cytokine whereas it
502 did not show any effects on the TNF- α -induced monocytes adhesion. This response may
503 be associated to the induction of MMP-12 which has been reported to induce the
504 recruitment of neutrophils in association with a transient increase in cytokines and
505 chemokines levels (33). Overall, these results were indicative of a general moderate
506 activation of the colon fibroblasts and of an inflammatory-like response after exposure
507 to the digested orange extract.

508 This study investigates the effects of a whole natural bitter orange extract. It is
509 important to determine the effects on the intestine of mixtures of flavonoids or of
510 mixtures of flavonoids with other compounds, since, complex mixtures of compounds
511 rather than single compounds are the most likely and frequent form in which these rich-
512 flavonoid natural extracts may be present in the intestinal lumen. Our study shows that
513 the major flavanones present in the bitter orange extract are not responsible for the
514 downregulation of PAI-1 in the colon cells although they contribute to the upregulation
515 of MMP-12. It is interesting to note that, individually, flavanones such as hesperidin or
516 naringenin do exert gene expression modulatory effects with specific anti-inflammatory

517 and anti-fibrotic effects. For example, hesperidin inhibited the TNF- α -induced VCAM-1
518 expression in endothelial cells (41) and naringenin reduced TGF- β 1-induced expression
519 of profibrotic genes, including PAI-1, in rat hepatic stellate cells (42). The mixture of
520 flavanones in the bitter orange extract tested here includes naringenin but did not induce
521 any changes on the expression of PAI-1 in the colon fibroblasts. Although we can not
522 discard that the different response may be caused by differences in the cell model or the
523 naringenin concentration used, these results indicate that it is necessary to determine the
524 effects of individual bioactive compounds as part of the mixtures or extracts which are
525 natural forms of consumption of these compounds. Our results also suggest that other
526 citrus components with reported anti-inflammatory properties such as polymethoxylated
527 flavones (43) may be present in the tested orange extract and may contribute to the
528 observed effects.

529 Plant derived bioactive compounds and/or bioactive-rich nutritional extracts are,
530 in principle, assumed to be of a preventive nature. Many studies looking at the anti-
531 inflammatory effects of these compounds or extracts have been mostly investigated
532 using *in vitro* and *in vivo* models of induced inflammation. However, the effects in
533 healthy normal tissues may be very different from those induced under pathological
534 conditions. One of the main physiological roles of intestine fibroblasts is to contribute
535 to the maintenance of the mucosal homeostasis, responding to daily challenge by
536 exogenous inflammation mediators (e.g. toxins, bacteria, etc) and leading to resolution
537 of the inflammation and tissue damage to avoid the inflammation from spreading and
538 causing a disease. The process is controlled by a complex spatio-temporal action of
539 many inflammatory mediators leading through progression of healing and resulting in
540 restitution of the gut barrier functions (15). The results presented here suggest that the
541 bitter orange extract tested in this study exerted moderate regulatory effects on the

542 activation of colon fibroblasts which may be beneficial in healthy normal cells to
543 prevent sustained inflammation. Fibroblasts ability to migrate and monocytes adhesion
544 were differentially affected by the treatment in unstimulated cells or in cells that had
545 been inflamed with TNF- α , suggesting that this orange extract may exert different
546 effects in healthy and in disease status. Further investigations are required to identify
547 the role *in vivo* of this *Citrus* derived extracts in the maintenance of the normal balance
548 in the human intestine and in the pathogenesis of inflammatory diseases.
549

550 **Acknowledgements**

551 We are very grateful to Jesús Cantalejo (Unidad de Genómica, Parque Científico de
552 Madrid, Fac. Biología, Universidad Complutense, Madrid, Spain) for his help with the
553 microarray analysis, Angel Gil (CEBAS-CSIC) for his assistance with the HPLC-DAD
554 analysis and to Francisco Borrego (Zoster S.A., Murcia, Spain) for his advice and
555 support throughout the project.

556

557 A complete listing of the probes with significant expression changes by microarrays
558 analysis with corresponding *p*-values, FDR-values and expression levels (ratio cells
559 treated with the extract/cells treated with control digesta; T/C) can be seen in
560 Supplementary Table 1. A summary of the top functions and pathways detected by the
561 Ingenuity Pathways Analysis is presented in Supplementary Table 2.

562

563 This work has been supported by Zoster S.A.(Murcia, Spain), and by the Projects
564 05556/PI/04 (Fundación Séneca, Murcia, Spain) and by CSD2007-00063 (Fun-C-Food;
565 Consolider Ingenio 2010). J.A.G.B. has a JAE fellowship from the Spanish ‘Consejo
566 Superior de Investigaciones Científicas’ (CSIC) and M.M.F. had a short term contract
567 from Zoster S.A.

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713 **Figures legend.**

714 **Figure 1.** Chemical structures of the major flavanones present in the bitter orange
715 extract.

716

717 **Figure 2.** Expression levels of selected genes modified in colon fibroblasts after 12 h or
718 24 h exposure to the digested bitter orange extract rich in flavanones. **A.** *GAPDH*
719 normalized relative gene expression changes (Treated/Control) by Affymetrix
720 microarrays and by RT-PCR (means \pm SD; n=3); **B.** *GAPDH* normalized protein levels
721 of the lysates from control and treated cells using Western blots. Values are the means \pm
722 SD (n=3 to n=7).

723

724 **Figure 3.** *GAPDH* normalized expression changes (Treated/Control) of PAI-1, MMP-
725 12 and SMURF2 in colon fibroblasts after exposure to undigested bitter orange extract
726 at the equivalent concentration of total flavanones (60 μ M) for 12 h, 24 h and 48 h. **A.**
727 Gene expression changes; **B.** protein changes. Values are the means \pm SD (n=3), **
728 ($p<0.01$) and * ($p<0.05$)

729

730 **Figure 4.** *GAPDH* normalized gene expression changes (Treated/Control) of *PAI-1*,
731 *MMP-12* and *SMURF2* in colon fibroblasts cultured in: i) EMEM culture medium
732 (0.1% FBS) + orange extract added 32 h after serum withdrawal; ii) EMEM culture
733 medium (0.1% FBS) + TNF- α (20 ng/mL) added 24 h after serum withdrawal; iii)
734 EMEM culture medium (0.1% FBS) + TNF- α (20 ng/mL) added 24 h after serum
735 withdrawal + orange extract added 8 h after TNF- α addition. RT-PCR analysis of
736 control and treated cells were performed after 56 h of incubation. Values are the means
737 \pm SD (n=3; ** ($p<0.01$)).

738

739 **Figure 5.** Effect of the flavanone-rich bitter orange extract on CCD-18Co migration
740 examined by wound healing assay. Colon fibroblasts monolayers were wounded at time
741 0 (**A**) and treated as follows: **B.** EMEM culture medium (10% FBS); **C.** EMEM culture
742 medium (0.1% FBS); **D.** EMEM culture medium (0.1% FBS) + TNF- α (20 ng/mL)
743 added 24 h after serum withdrawal; **E.** EMEM culture medium (0.1% FBS) + orange
744 extract added 32 h after serum withdrawal; **F.** EMEM culture medium (0.1% FBS) +
745 TNF- α (20 ng/mL) added 24 h after serum withdrawal + orange extract added 8 h after
746 TNF- α addition. Photographs of control and treated cells were taken after 56 h of
747 incubation. Results are representative of 2 to 4 independent experiments.

748

749 **Figure 6.** Effect of the flavanone-rich bitter orange extract on monocytes adhesion to
750 the colon fibroblasts. The adhesion of calcein-labelled THP-1 monocytes to CCD-18Co
751 colon fibroblasts was quantitated using a fluorescence-detecting microplate reader. Data
752 are presented as the mean \pm SD of at least three independent experiments ** ($p < 0.01$).

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Table 1. Total Flavanones Recovered from the Stomach, Small Intestine and Colon of Rats Dosed With Orange Extract.

Time points ¹	Stomach content	Small Intestine content	Colon	Total
1	20.6 ² (32.6%) ³	11.4 (18.1%)	n.d.	32.0 (50.7%)
2	24.0 (38.0%)	9.0 (14.3%)	0.08 (0.13%)	33.0 (52.3%)
6	17.6 (27.9%)	10.8 (17.1%)	17.1 (27.1%)	45.5 (72.1%)
12	10.2 (16.2%)	0.8 (1.3%)	9.8 (15.5%)	20.8 (32.9%)
24	0.5 (0.80%)	0.04 (<0.06%)	0.4 (0.6%)	0.9 (1.5%)

¹: hours after the dose; ²: mg; ³: % of the administered dose of flavanones; n.d.: not detected.

Table 2. Selection of Probes With Significant Expression Changes in Human Colon Fibroblasts Exposed to a Flavanones-Enriched Orange Extract and Involved in Immune Response and Tissue Repair.

Affymetrix probe	Gene symbol	Gene name	Ratio T/C
<i>ECM components</i>			
211343_s_at	<i>COL13A1</i>	collagen, type XIII, alpha 1	0.6
217430_x_at	<i>COL1A1</i>	collagen, type I, alpha 1	0.7
202404_s_at	<i>COL1A2</i>	collagen, type I, alpha 2	0.8
212488_at	<i>COL5A1</i>	collagen, type V, alpha 1	0.7
37892_at	<i>COL11A1</i>	collagen, type XI, alpha 1	1.4
211981_at	<i>COL4A1</i>	collagen, type IV, alpha 1	1.6
214641_at	<i>COL4A3</i>	collagen, type IV, alpha 3 (Goodpasture antigen)	1.3
227048_at	<i>LAMA1</i>	laminin, alpha 1	1.6
204580_at	<i>MMP12</i>	matrix metalloproteinase 12 (macrophage elastase)	2.1
<i>Growth Factors and related genes</i>			
210311_at	<i>FGF5</i>	fibroblast growth factor 5	0.6
203821_at	<i>HBEGF</i>	heparin-binding EGF-like growth factor	0.5
210095_s_at	<i>IGFBP3</i>	insulin-like growth factor binding protein 3	0.7
208944_at	<i>TGFBR2</i>	transforming growth factor, beta receptor II (70/80kDa)	0.7
209946_at	<i>VEGFC</i>	endothelial growth factor C	0.7
205239_at	<i>AREG</i>	amphiregulin (schwannoma-derived growth factor)	2.2
228121_at	<i>TGFB2</i>	transforming growth factor, beta 2	1.3
204731_at	<i>TGFB3</i>	transforming growth factor, beta receptor III	1.5
<i>Interleukins</i>			
206924_at	<i>IL11</i>	interleukin 11	1.3
205067_at	<i>IL1B</i>	interleukin 1, beta	1.7
202948_at	<i>IL1R1</i>	interleukin 1 receptor, type I	1.7
206569_at	<i>IL24</i>	interleukin 24	1.6
205207_at	<i>IL6</i>	interleukin 6 (interferon, beta 2)	1.6
202859_x_at,	<i>IL8</i>	interleukin 8	1.5
231779_at	<i>IRAK2</i>	interleukin-1 receptor-associated kinase 2	1.5
<i>Chemokines</i>			
205476_at	<i>CCL20</i>	chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 20	1.6
204470_at	<i>CXCL1</i>	chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 1	1.7
204533_at	<i>CXCL10</i>	chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 10	2.2
210163_at	<i>CXCL11</i>	chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 11	1.9
209774_x_at	<i>CXCL2</i>	chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 2	2.2
207850_at	<i>CXCL3</i>	chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 3	2.4
215101_s_at	<i>CXCL5</i>	chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 5	3.1
206336_at	<i>CXCL6</i>	chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 6	1.9
<i>Proteases inhibitors</i>			
202628_s_at	<i>SERPINE1</i>	serpin peptidase inhibitor, clade E (nexin, plasminogen activator inhibitor type 1), member 1	0.4
212268_at	<i>SERPINB1</i>	serpin peptidase inhibitor, clade B (ovalbumin), member 1	1.4
212190_at	<i>SERPINE2</i>	serpin peptidase inhibitor, clade E (nexin, plasminogen activator inhibitor type 1), member 2	1.7
<i>Prostaglandins synthases</i>			
207388_s_at	<i>PTGES</i>	prostaglandin E synthase	2.1
204748_at	<i>PTGS2</i>	prostaglandin-endoperoxide synthase 2 (prostaglandin G/H synthase and cyclooxygenase)	1.7

Figure 1.

Flavanone	R1	R2	R3	mg/g extract
Naringin	H	OH	ONeo ^a	245
Neohesperidin	OH	OCH ₃	ONeo	114
Hesperidin	OH	OCH ₃	ORut ^b	17
Naringenin	H	OH	OH	4
Hesperetin	OH	OCH ₃	OH	4
Isosakuranetin	H	OCH ₃	OH	2

^aNeohesperidose; ^brutinoside.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

TNF- α	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+
Orange extract	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

